

Cultural Survival and Political Struggle: Insights from the Documentary

The Tibet Within

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Abstract

Tibet claims that it has been forcefully occupied by China since 1951 with a well-planned strategy to destroy its national and cultural identity. On the contrary, China asserts that Tibet has always been an inseparable part of China and dismisses the argument that it forcibly annexed it. China claims that it has focused on the growth and infrastructure developments in Tibet but Tibetans refute this claim. Instead, the Tibetans vouch for severe human rights violations and cultural genocide carried out by China in Tibet. The paper attempts to study the key issues addressed in the documentary film *The Tibet Within*, made by Eva Cirnu, a Canadian filmmaker. Through this study, the researchers attempt to analyse how the film represents Tibet and strive to find out the ways by which Tibetans carry out their struggle for freedom as depicted in the documentary film. The researchers conducted thematic content analysis of the film and found that the film stresses on two key aspects: the repression of Tibetans, their language and culture in their homelands; and the struggles of those in exile to preserve the Tibetan identity and culture.

Keywords: China, Culture, Documentary Film, Human Rights, Identity, Language, Protest, Religious Freedom, Tibet, Torture

Introduction

The Tibet Within is a documentary film directed by Eva Cirnu a Canadian Filmmaker. The 57 minutes and 29 seconds long documentary film is an attempt to narrate the stories of the Tibetans living in exile. The documentary film is the representation of Tibetans in exile by a non-Tibetan-non-Chinese documentary filmmaker.

The status of Tibet continues to be one of the most important conflict issues for both China and Tibet. China strongly claims that Tibet is an inseparable part whereas Tibet maintains that historically Tibet was an independent nation and that China forcibly annexed it (Sperling, 2004). China and Tibet continue to stand by the polarized historical narratives. Justice - injustice in Tibet continues to remain a burning question in all debates and discussions. Even though Tibet- China conflict has been discussed majorly as a territorial issue, there is a need for an in-depth analysis which goes beyond the political realm into the social, economic, cultural, environmental and humanitarian aspects.

According to Barry Sautman (2006, p. 244) Tibet's culture has been at utmost risk for all these years and has faced genocide for long. The International Commission of Jurists (ICJ) recognises that Tibet has undergone genocides, especially cultural genocide. ICJ defines cultural genocide as “ any of the following acts committed with intent to destroy, in whole or in part, a national, ethnic, racial or religious group's cultural integrity, historical way of life, heritage and significant cultural traditions, or the group's internationally vouchsafed right to self-determination: (a) killing members of the group; (b) causing serious bodily or mental harm to members of the group; (c) deliberately inflicting on the group conditions calculated to bring about destruction of the aforementioned cultural values in whole or in part; (d) imposing measures intended to prevent births within the groups; (e) forcibly transferring children of the group to be indoctrinated in the culture of another group” (ICT, 2012).

Article 2 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) states, “Everyone is entitled to all the rights and freedoms set forth in this Declaration, without distinction of any kind, such as race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status. Furthermore, no distinction shall be made on the basis of the political, jurisdictional or international status of the country or territory to which a person belongs, whether it be independent, trust, non-self-governing or under any other limitation of sovereignty.” China has curbed human rights of Tibetans inside Tibet on numerous accounts as reported widely by the international media.

The West's interest in Tibet has a long history, dating back to the 18th century when the concept of "tibétophilie européenne" or European Tibetophilia became popular with the

publishing of some of the first accounts of people who travelled to Tibet (Kaschewsky, 2001, pp. 3-4). Tibetan religious beliefs and practices were also widespread in the New Age Movement, which began in the nineteenth century and resurfaced in the 1960s and 1970s (Korom, 1997). Hollywood, in particular, has played a significant role in influencing Western perceptions of Tibet. Richard Gere and Sharon Stone, both well-known Hollywood actors, have emphasised on the issue by making personal pro-Tibet remarks (Chan, 2009, p. 69). More notably, feature and documentary films on Tibet have been produced, like John Noel's *Climbing Mount Everest* (1922), Frank Capra's *Lost Horizon* (1937), Jean-Jacques Annaud's *Seven Years in Tibet* (1997), Martin Scorsese's *Kundun* (1997) and Eric Valli's *Himalaya* (1999).

Tibet has been the subject of cinematic interest since the 1990s; the 1950s were the first period of prosperity for Tibetan documentary films, when socialist, realist documentaries were heavily pushed by the Chinese government. Films on Tibet were largely made by state-run studios at that time, and hence were influenced by state ideology (Tan, 2016). The effort to broaden the notion of Tibetan subjects or Tibetan lives often confronts narratives of suitable identity put out by different sources, including the Tibetan government in exile, the Chinese government, and outsiders looking in, including filmmakers and other cultural producers. Tibetans reject foreign views of Tibetan history and identity by stepping outside the government-in-"selected exile's tradition" (Hobsbawm & Ranger, 1983). At the same time, through their films, they invoke aspects of Tibetan identity and reclaim the forgotten past.

From a Tibetan perspective, the genre and the imaginativeness of the director are not important instead the significant concern is about how the film represents Tibet and what is depicted about Tibetans. Though not a compulsion, the criteria may consider the degree of involvement of the Tibetans in making the film (Barnett, 2002).

Tibet has attracted Western as well as Chinese filmmakers who have portrayed Tibet on the basis of their understanding and requirement. Tibetans living outside of Tibet are creating visual representations of their exile. Other notions regarding Tibetanness, whether official (supported by the exile government), Chinese, or international, are reinscribed and countered in these fictional and nonfictional products (Durke, 2006).

Objectives of the Study

This paper attempts to study the documentary film *The Tibet Within* with the following objectives:

1. To analyse the key issues addressed in the documentary film through various emerging themes.
2. To understand how Tibetans are fighting for freedom as depicted in the documentary film.

Theoretical Framework

The researchers have applied Orientalism (1978), the concept introduced by Edward Said to study the dominant discourses through which Tibet is represented by a western documentary filmmaker. The concept focuses on how the film replicates the exotic narratives and the manufacturing the idea of the “Other.” The study has also used Stuart Hall’s Representation Theory (Hall, 1997) to find out how the film constructs narratives about Tibet. The framework provides a detailed analysis of how Tibet is represented by the West.

Methodology

For this study, the researchers have conducted the Thematic Content Analysis of the documentary film, *The Tibet Within* made by a Canadian filmmaker, Eva Cirnu. The film has been produced in two versions, the first in English language and the second in French language. Both the versions of the documentary film are available on YouTube.com. For this study, the English language version was selected. After the careful analysis and coding of the data, following themes were generated:

- a. Human Rights Violations
- b. Tibetan Identity, Language and Culture
- c. Religious Freedom
- d. Tibet and International Community
- e. Tibetan Protest

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The five themes generated after the careful analysis of the data are discussed below:

1. Human Rights Violations

In the documentary film, the narrator shares that the Tibetans inside Tibet have been stripped of the fundamental human rights. When the artists, writers and activists fight for the preservation of their culture and religion, they are aware of the risk associated with it; the risk

of imprisonment, torture, and death. The narrator reveals the story of Tashi Rapten, a writer and editor of a banned literary magazine who was detained in 2010 because of his writings. He was sentenced to four years in prison and there is no information about his whereabouts and well-being. The narrator also shares the case of Kunga Tsayang, a writer, monk, photographer & environmental activist who was detained in 2009 and sentenced to five years in prison and his whereabouts are also unknown. The documentary film also reveals the case of Tsering Woesser, Tibetan author, poet & blogger who was honored with the prestigious International Woman of Courage Award in 2013 but China denied her passport necessary for travelling to the United States to receive the award. Another incident of arbitrary arrest of Paljor Norbu, master printer of Buddhist text who was arrested at the age of 81 and sentenced to seven years imprisonment was revealed in the film.

In the film, Lhamo Tso, wife of Dhondup Wangchen, known for filming the 2008 documentary *Leaving Fear Behind*, narrates her ordeal after Wangchen was arrested for making the documentary film. She says that her husband made the documentary film in which he recorded the reactions of Tibetans towards the Olympic games to be held in Beijing in the year 2008 and also the feeling of Tibetans towards the Dalai Lama. As soon as his documentary film came out, he was imprisoned and sentenced to 6 years in jail. Since, his arrest in 2010, she has spoken publicly about it, many times in Europe, North America and other countries. Tso reveals that at the beginning of Wangchen's sentence, he was forced to work seventeen hours per day. But, ever since Wangchen's story became public, his treatment in prison improved.

The documentary film highlights the need for bringing out the truth about the situation in Tibet. Sherab Woesser, Editor in Chief, Phayul, shares that the aim of his publication is to bring out news from Tibet which is closest to the truth and reality. However, he admits that it is difficult to communicate with people inside Tibet as there are chances of endangering the safety and security of people inside Tibet. Woesser shares that while selecting the stories for publishing, it is important to keep the repercussions in mind. He also informs that people are under strict surveillance everywhere, on the streets, inside the monasteries, in every alley, so one has to be careful.

Many participants in the documentary film raise concern about the human rights violations like curtailment of freedom of expression and arbitrary detentions carried out by China inside Tibet. In the documentary film, one of the participants, Dorothy Hu, founder of Hong-Kong Stand with Tibet, also an art-teacher in India, shares her personal feelings about the situation in Tibet. She confesses, "Every day when I read the news, I feel very sad because China have so many suppressions. People get arrested. When I go through the list of people dying or

arrested, they get hurt and the number, you can't imagine is a lot, a lot and when I see those Tibetan, they have no choice because in China they don't have rights to voice out. Media get blocked, they can't go inside to interview and even though media would like to help, but China being very rude and saying no! not welcome and just treat those Tibetans like a prisoner and not as a human being and I think as a human being it is very unfair to them. We need to respect everybody's human rights (sic)."

The filmmaker highlights the issue of press censorship in Tibet. A clipping of Penpa Tsering, the then Speaker of Tibetan Parliament in exile at a press conference in 2013 is included in the documentary where Tsering exposes the press censorship imposed by China in Tibet. During the conference, he reveals that Tibet is in a lock-down and no press can go there. He also apprises that no international fact-finding delegation can visit Tibet and there are no witnesses to what is happening inside Tibet. He further explains that the international press demands evidence of what is happening inside Tibet. China being aware of the fact, makes all efforts to prevent such evidence gathering by preventing people from visiting Tibet.

The documentary film presents the personal story of Soepa Phuntsok, former Tibetan monk and political prisoner who spent 5 years in Chinese prison. Phuntsok shares his prison experience in Drapachi, Lhasa. He tells, "...there were 1300 to 1400 prisoners. 400 of them were political prisoners. While I was in prison, I was beaten by the Chinese policemen and confined to a cell." The participants in the film also share the reasons behind escaping from Tibet. M. Lobsang, the then Secretary-Namgyal Monastery in Dharamsala narrates that he was born in Tibet and escaped to India in the year 2000 where he joined the monastery in 2005. He revealed that he paid a guide who helped him and 23 others to escape to India after crossing the snow mountains. It took the group 20 days and lots of difficulties to reach India via Nepal. He admits that living in exile is safer than living in China occupied Tibet as Tibetans do not have freedom to exercise their rights.

2. Identity, Language and Culture

The documentary film focuses on the importance and need for preserving Tibetan culture, identity and language. The film raises concerns of the Tibetans living in exile who strive hard to preserve the Tibetan culture which continues to face severe threat under the Chinese occupation. Dr. Lobsang Sangay, former Prime Minister of Tibetan Government in Exile narrates why Tibetan culture and language is under threat in Tibet and also emphasizes on the need for protecting and preserving the Tibetan language and culture. He says, "The Tibetan

language as a medium of instruction is not allowed at the university level or high school level, even the middle school level, now only available in primary school level because they are in remote villages. Tibetan was used as a medium of instruction, that is also discouraged. That is why you see, students coming out in the streets. So, Tibetan language is very much under threat in Tibet, under the occupation of Chinese. Hence, is very important that Tibetan language ought to preserve and protect it inside Tibet particularly but also in exile (sic).”

M. Lobsang, also acknowledges that the Tibetan culture and religion are in danger inside Tibet. He confirms that most of the schools are Chinese and the language of medium is Chinese which minimizes the chances of learning Tibetan. He adds that some of the children go to the monastery to learn Tibetan. The narrator of the documentary film explains that Tibetans inside Tibet are not permitted to follow their traditional lifestyle. The Tibetan traditional clothes and lifestyle are under threat which is why the exile community tries to preserve and promote the traditional clothes. The Folk museum Tibetan Institute of Performing Arts (TIPA) in Dharamsala features traditional costumes from all Tibetan areas. This is crucial for the Tibetan community in exile since many of the Tibetan traditional clothes, specifically related to lifestyles are now under threat.

Tenzin Tsundue, Tibetan activist & writer who lives in Dharamsala India, explains the Lhakar movement started by monks, nuns, nomads and students in Tibet who decided to celebrate Wednesday as a soul day. He narrates that the Tibetans decided to hold a special prayer for his Holiness the Dalai Lama. On that day, they wear Tibetan dress, speak Tibetan language, sing Tibetan songs and celebrate the Tibetan identity. He mentions that the movement has been inspiring and did not cost any Tibetan life. He shares that, “This celebration of culture was not only a source of pride and sense of identity for the young Tibetans, it was culturally empowering. Now, here is a movement that is bringing Tibetans to their own roots, to their culture, to their language, to their religion.”

The documentary film reveals that the greatest challenge faced by Tibetans in exile is the preservation of their culture, identity and language. The Tibetan population living in exile has constantly tried to keep their traditional art forms alive. The Tibetan community in exile has established art centers where they train hundreds of people in Tibetan art forms with a sense of urgency but also timeless patience. To preserve visual arts in exile, Tibetans have built institutions that are dedicated to the preservation and promotion of Tibetan songs, dance forms and costumes. In the documentary film, Dicki Chhoyang, former Information and International Relationship Minister, Tibetan Government in exile, highlights that there is a genuine threat to Tibetan culture and further explains that Tibet is being forced to integrate and assimilate. The

Tibetan language today serves no greater practical purpose and has been limited to songs and dance. There is practically no official use of Tibetan language which is why it is obvious that in matter of no time, the use of Tibetan language will diminish inside Tibet under Chinese occupation and in exile. The language faces danger in exile too because the Tibetan community lives in different host countries with different languages and cultures. Maintaining the native language in a foreign land is a big challenge.

The narrator apprises the viewers about the impressive online database in the United States that preserves and displays thousands of digitized literature, history and religious works brought from Tibet by refugees. The Tibetan Buddhist Resource Centre is a database of over 7 million pages, getting thousands of visitors daily. It exemplifies the Dalai Lama's call to be 21st century Buddhist by using contemporary technologies in order to preserve the ancient wisdom and tradition.

The film highlights the traditional, nomadic way of Tibetan life but also reveals how the traditional culture is under threat after the occupation of Tibet by China. N. Choedak, the former Secretary, Department of religion and Culture, Tibetan government in exile, admits that had he been in Tibet, he would have been a herdsman and not the secretary of department of religion as he hailed from a nomadic family and owned agricultural land. He further urges the world to understand the problems of Tibetans inside Tibet and extend their support. He says, "If we are able to gain our objective, this will give lot of inspiration to the future generations. Not only for Tibetans but whole of the world where by we can create really a peaceful, harmonious, loving atmosphere and society which we need." He also mentions that before 1959, when Tibet was independent, there was no need for a department of religion and culture but after the Chinese occupation and systematic destruction in Tibet, it became necessary to establish the department in exile.

3. Religious Freedom

The documentary film brings forward the personal narratives of Tibetans who have escaped from Tibet to India. One Tibetan refugee (identity undisclosed) shares her experience when she returned to Tibet after attending the Kal Chakra. She says, "...Once the Kal Chakra was over, I went back and was arrested. The police then asked me if I had gone to meet the Dalai Lama. I had many things with me. I left them and was taken to prison in Shigatse. Several people in our group from Amdo didn't have passports. Usually, the passport requests get denied. We were close to Losar (Tibetan New Year). In the group, there were many women,

around 75 to 80 years old, and also children, about 15 years old. We had nothing to eat, in prison. Now if we apply for passports, I request are denied because we have attended the Kal Chakra teachings (sic).” Her personal experience reveals that China suppresses religious freedom in Tibet.

Another Tibetan refugee who escaped from Amdo region in Tibet reveals that in recent times, there have been several incidents of self-immolations in Amdo province. He shares that the Tibetans are carrying out these self-immolations as they have no freedom of speech, no freedom of religion, no freedom to use their culture or language and no right to travel when and how they want to. He further shares that the Tibetans have the greatest faith in the Dalai Lama who is their greatest master but unfortunately, the Tibetans inside Tibet are not allowed to even keep his photograph or exercise the right to assemble for holding prayers ceremonies for the Dalai Lama. He also informs that there are many great lamas in Tibet but it is difficult for them to practice religion or teach. He reveals that if the Tibetan lamas want to organize any ceremony or teach, they must seek permission from the Chinese officials in the city. They also have to guarantee the Chinese officials that there would be no trouble during such a programme.

M. Lobsang reveals that whenever there are major religious activities, Chinese authorities are always present and they control the public, making it very difficult for the Tibetans. The documentary film also highlights that Buddhist monasteries in Tibet are under strict surveillance. There are cameras all around capturing the religious activities. Since the Chinese occupation, religious persecution in Tibet has escalated. The monasteries are being managed and controlled by the Chinese Communist Party (CCP). The Chinese government compel the Tibetan nuns and monks to denounce their spiritual leader, The Dalai Lama. The film highlights that despite the pressure from the Chinese government, monks and nuns continue to lead the struggle for the preservation of Tibetan culture and religion. The film reveals that despite being subjected to regular re-education campaigns by the CCP, they continue to dedicate and even sacrifice their lives towards the preservation of their religion, identity and culture.

Soepa Phuntsok, explains that the Chinese sentenced him to five years imprisonment and tortured him because they wanted to reform his religious thoughts, however, the Chinese failed to do so. The primary reason behind his arrest was that the former monk was working towards the preservation of Tibetan religion and culture.

4. Support from International Community

The documentary film focusses on the relationship between Tibetans and the international community. The film highlights that the Tibetan community in exile is grateful towards India for providing them the greatest support. Tenzin Tsundue, Tibetan writer & activist in exile appreciates India for supporting the exiled Tibetans. He says, “Government of India unlike any other country has actually given the exiled Tibetans the most support. Not only physically with all the infrastructure, even given us the freedom to nurture and grow.”

The documentary film comprises stories of non-Tibetans from the West and their relationship with Tibet. It portrays the relationship people have developed with the culture and religion of Tibet. Participants share how their relationship with Tibet has evolved with time and also admit their admiration for the rich cultural heritage, spirituality and religion. They also express their concern over the Tibetan struggle for freedom. Dorit Dornier, Artist, owner of Galerie Mazarine, Montreal, Canada, shares how she was intrigued by the mysterious Tibet; a country hidden in the Himalayas with thousands of monasteries. She reveals that the peaceful Buddha statues attracted her and she started to explore the same. During the process, she understood that Tibetan sculptures were symbol of peace, compassion and love. However, she also reveals that when she started working on the Tibetan sculptures, it was addressed as Tibetan-culture but now the sculptures are labelled as Chinese-Tibetan and this transition makes her sad. Another participant, Tomoyo Ihaya, a visual artist from Vancouver, Canada, shares that she has a close relationship with the Tibetan community. She shares that she was pained to learn about the self-immolations by Tibetans and the situation inside Tibet motivated her to start painting the political, social and environmental situation in Tibet. She further expresses deep concern about Chinese government digging all the mines, contaminating the waters, dumping nuclear waste and forcefully taking land from the nomadic people in Tibet.

The film highlights the role of several organisations like the Canada Tibet Committee (CTC), Tibetan Cultural Association of Quebec, Montreal, Tibetan Resettlement Project, Ottawa and Friends of Tibet, Ottawa in preserving and promoting the Tibetan culture, language and cause. Non-Tibetan volunteers from these organisations share their experiences and stories of association with Tibet in the film. One of the participants, Carole Samdup, Executive Director, CTC mentions that the work of CTC is to promote and advance the Tibetan culture in Canada, firstly, because it a fascinating culture and secondly, it is at risk of extinction in Tibet itself. She further shares that CTC has invited the Dalai Lama on several occasions to speak about the ethics for the new millennia, secularism, education, peace and compassion. His teachings represent the core element of the Tibetan culture therefore, such talks and sessions, also aim to encourage the international institutions like the United Nations to protect Tibetan

heritage and culture. Samdup further explains that CTC has also started a campaign to encourage UNESCO's world heritage committee to take steps to ensure that the China protects heritage sites in all parts of Lhasa, particularly the area of Jokhang temple. The organization has appealed to UNESCO to include parts of Old Lhasa on an endangered list and also to send an investigative team to Lhasa to review the situation. On local level, CTC organizes cultural days with the objective of celebrating Tibetan music, Tibetan food, Tibetan crafts. Tibetan art, craft, and culture is very popular with the Canadians who continue to participate in such celebrations year after year. The narrator informs about the Tibetan community of Montreal which is a small group of one hundred very active members. The members regularly organize Tibetan dance, music shows and also hold Tibetan language classes. The second generation of Tibetans born in exile accompany their parents to the rallies and vigils for the Tibetan cause.

Barb Haddad a volunteer for Friends of Tibet in Ottawa, shares the story of her association with Tibet. She says, "12 years ago, I travelled the world and I had the opportunity to visit Tibet for one week on a tour and I had read stories previously on Tibet and I was fully aware of the situation in Tibet and knew that a chain of mountains separated me from Tibetans and so as I was walking, I was imagining how people would escape that area and come seek freedom in Nepal and India. And it humbled me because I had met Tibetans on that path. We as tourists pay for these trips but when the Tibetans escaped, they came with barely anything, they stopped in the hills, in the mountains and froze sometimes to death or lost the finger and ears, parts of their bodies just to find freedom."

The film includes video clip of Dr Lobsang Sangay, the then Prime Minister of Tibetan government in Exile while he is addressing a press conference in 2013. During the conference he expresses his concern over not receiving concrete support from the International community. He says, "Tibetans are suffering immensely yet we subscribe to non-violence, democracy, we subscribe to dialogue as a mean to solve the issue of Tibet. Tibet is a test for the International Community. We subscribe to and we have been practicing democracy, non-violence from the past many decades. Generally, international community praise democracy and non-violence as the best means to govern one's community and lead one's movement. Tibetans have been doing it for decades. Yet, concrete steps, support from international community is comparatively behind what we see in Syria or other places. When international media project many of the seniors who are given guns as freedom fighters trying to overthrow Assad, it makes us wonder what is the priority?"

N. Choedak also asserts the need for more significant international support. He raises concern about the insufficient response received by Tibet from the international community

despite 95 self-immolations between 2009 and 2012. He says, “It is only for the sake of religion and culture that they have self-immolated. We are not getting any satisfactory reaction from the world community... And more importantly, we in exile are not able to convey the message of those who have left a message...They want His Holiness The Dalai Lama back to Tibet. They want Tibetan religion and culture to be protected. They want freedom, they want human rights in Tibet (sic).”

5. Tibetan Protest

The documentary film reveals that primarily Tibetans have practiced and promoted non-violent and peaceful protests to highlight their struggle. The film unveils the several ways of protests used by Tibetans like candle marches, rallies, and demonstrations during which the peaceful protestors raise slogans with the objective of creating awareness about the grim situation inside Tibet. Slogans like ‘No human rights in Tibet’, ‘No religious freedom in Tibet’, ‘Shame on China’, ‘World is watching, shame on China’ and ‘Stop genocide in Tibet’ are used during the protest marches and demonstrations.

The narrator explains that despite becoming a minority in their own country, Tibetans pursue their peaceful struggle with renewed strength and determination without ever compromising their commitment to non-violence. The documentary film highlights that Tibetans are performing self-immolations as a protest tool against Chinese occupation and human rights violations in Tibet.

Dorjee Tseten, the then Director of Students for Free Tibet, Asia apprises that the Lhakar movement has turned into non-cooperation or civil disobedience movement. Tibetan movement has become a global movement being carried out to re-establishing the Tibetan identity. Movements like Lhakar are wonderful way to connect Tibetans inside Tibet with Tibetans living in exile. The film stresses on the non-violent protest methods used by the Tibetans in their struggle. Tenzin Tsundue shares that Tibetans do not possess guns. They do not require guns as they already have love and compassion, the two tools that will lead the Tibetans to a free Tibet.

Conclusion

This paper has strived to understand the key issues of the Tibetan struggle as depicted in the documentary film *The Tibet Within: Tibetan struggle in Exile*. The documentary film highlights Tibetan people's struggle and their valiant efforts to maintain their culture. It

concentrates on two aspects: Tibetan people's persecution, language and culture in their homelands, and the efforts of those in the diaspora to keep them alive. The resolution of the problems in Tibet should be considered one of the most important issues of our day, because, while everyone else appears to have resorted to violence to attain their goals, Tibetans have only engaged in nonviolent rallies, lobbying, and reconciliation endeavours. The personal stories and experiences of many Tibetans who have either been imprisoned or tortured highlights the grim situation inside Tibet where Tibetans are subjected to human rights violations. Tibet is under strict surveillance by the Chinese government. Tibetans do not enjoy fundamental rights like right to freedom of speech and expression, right to movement, right to practice religion, right to promote and preserve culture and language. The film reveals that the human rights situation in Tibet is grim as several incidents of arbitrary arrest, detention, imprisonment, torture and disappearance are mentioned in the film.

There is urgent need to preserve Tibetan culture, identity and language. The participants of the documentary film comprise members of the Tibetan government in exile, activists, monks and former political prisoners who have repeatedly raised concern about the Chinese oppression inside Tibet. Through various personal narratives, the film raises concern about the threat to Tibetan culture, identity and language inside Tibet as well as in exile. The Tibetan community living in exile are committed to promote and preserve Tibetan culture, identity and language. It is important to strengthen the relationship with Tibetan as well as Non-Tibetan volunteers who support the Tibetan cause. The international media has attempted to report the human rights abuse in Tibet by the Chinese authorities. In a photo feature published by Associated Press, (AP, 2021) Tibetan traditions are under serious threat. In the name of growth and development, the Tibetans are being forced to change their way of life, compelled to learn Chinese and curtail their religious activities. The Chinese Communist Party says that there has been infrastructural development in Tibet however, critics suggest that the Tibetan identity is under threat.

The documentary film reveals that the Tibetan monks and nuns inside Tibet do not have the right to practice Buddhism freely. The Chinese authorities control the functioning of the monasteries. China condemns the Dalai Lama and compels the Tibetans to denounce him. The Tibetans are not permitted to even keep photographs of the Dalai Lama. The re-education campaign started by China is a strategic tool to change the religious beliefs of the Tibetans. According to a report published by India today (Kannan , 2020) China is forcing a number of Tibetan nomads to shift to training facilities popularly known as labour camps where they are

subjected to enforced indoctrination. China has reportedly banned all religious activities of Tibetan party members in the Amdo region in Tibet (ANI, 2021).

The documentary film highlights that even though the Tibetans in exile are living in several countries, they continue to seek formidable support from the international community. The exile government urges the international community to take cognizance of the grim situation inside Tibet and take appropriate action against China. The Tibetans continue to request the United Nations and government of the US and UK to intervene and recognise China's forceful occupation of Tibet. In 2021, Tibetans in exile have come together to protest against the Winter Olympics to be held in Beijing in 2022. They have urged the world leaders to boycott the games because of the growing human rights violations against Tibetans and other ethnic minorities by China. The Tibetan government in exile believes that there is urgent threat of cultural genocide in Tibet and the international community must act against China (Cadell & Miglani, 2021).

The paper has also attempted to understand how Tibetans are fighting for freedom as depicted in the documentary film. The documentary film highlights that despite facing long suppression and torture, Tibetans continue to fight non-violently against the Chinese occupation and oppression. The Tibetans organise peaceful protests, demonstrations, candle marches, non-violent rallies, to raise concern about the Tibet issue. The self-immolations performed by the Tibetans portrays the strength of their resilience and struggle. So far, 159 Tibetans have performed the act of self-immolations (ANI, 2022). Tibetans carry out symbolic protests against the Chinese oppression by carrying the Tibetan flag during peaceful marches and candle vigils. Reportedly, China has banned the use of prayer flags in the Qinghai's Golog region and Tengchen county under the banner of "behavioural reform" programme (RFA, 2020).

The authoritative power of documentary films, allow the filmmakers to present what they uncover and believe and what they want others to unravel and trust as a result of their representations (Grant, 1998). Any individual can be a member of any specific public if one attempts to communicate with other people and discuss about the common problems (Aufderheide, 2007). In the case of *The Tibet Within: Tibetan Struggle in Exile*, Eva Cirnu has attempted to become a part of the Tibetan community by allowing the participants to highlight the issues concerning the members of the Tibetan community in exile. According to Bill Nichols, (2001) when the filmmaker conducts interviews of subjects in order to understand them, she or he is able to participate in the process and present a wider perspective of the issue. Through this documentary, the filmmaker has attempted to present the concerns of the Tibetans

living in exile and the film is able to connect with the hardships of Tibetans living inside Tibet. Through the film, Cirnu weaves an emotional narrative of the Tibetans desirous of support from the world against the Chinese forceful occupation and suppression.

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